

EU Mission Cancer

Cancer affects individuals of all ages, genders, and social standings, posing a significant challenge. The EU Mission on Cancer is a Horizon Europe collaborative effort bringing together and aligning a portfolio of cancer-centered research and innovation projects with the ambition of improving the lives of over 3 million people by 2030.

Four key objectives:

Gathering a deeper understanding of cancer

Facilitating the prevention and early detection of the disease

Developing improved methods for diagnosis and treatment

Enhancing the quality of life for patients and their families

PREVENTION AND EARLY DETECTION CLUSTER

SCAN THE QR TO LEARN MORE ABOUT THE CLUSTER

Funded by the European Union

"The six projects (CPW, PIECES, PREVENT, CO-CAPTAIN, 4PCAN, ONCODIR) that form the Prevention & Early Detection cluster are funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe - Research and Innovation funding programme (2021 - 2027). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor of the individual projects that constitute the cluster. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them"

PREVENTION AND EARLY DETECTION CLUSTER

The Prevention and Early Detection Cluster is a collaborative approach aiming to coordinate and integrate the efforts of six different cancer prevention projects. Together, **they work to increase societal and policy impact on preventing and detecting cancer early.** This initiative falls under the EU Mission on Cancer.

Each project addresses unique challenges in cancer prevention, from mental health to occupational health surveillance. **They integrate primary prevention programs into existing systems,** highlighting their different methodologies and target populations. All ensure a holistic approach to achieving the Cancer Mission's objectives and improving the quality of life of EU citizens.

The size and colour of the circle represents the number of projects involved

Cluster

- 1. Co-CAPTAIN.** Cancer prevention among individuals with mental ill-health: co-adapting and implementing patient navigation for primary cancer prevention.
- 2. Cancer Prevention at Work (CPW).** Occupational health surveillance in the implementation of prevention of infection-related cancer.
- 3. ONCODIR.** Evidence-based Participatory Decision Making for Cancer Prevention through implementation research.
- 4. PREVENT.** Improving and upscaling primary prevention of cancer by addressing childhood obesity through implementation research-the PREVENT approach.
- 5. 4P-CAN.** Personalized CANcer Primary Prevention research through Citizen Participation and digitally enabled social innovation.
- 6. PIECES.** Towards large-scale adaptation and tailored implementation of evidence-based primary cancer prevention programmes in Europe and beyond.

The Prevention and Early Detection Cluster goals:

- 1: Provide citizens with primary affordable cancer prevention interventions through adapted local, regional and national health protocols that consider their sustainability, feasibility, cost-effectiveness, accessibility and affordability.
- 2: Identify the main challenges and risks that might hinder the adoption and implementation of cancer prevention programmes.
- 3: Educate healthcare professionals and patient organisations with evidence-based cancer prevention information that would facilitate the cancer patient family's companionship and support.
- 4: Involve all relevant stakeholders in the identification, research and evaluation of barriers and its outcomes.
- 5: Develop policy recommendations aimed at informing policy and decision-makers.
- 6: Design and facilitate evidence-based interventions in collaboration with authorities at local, regional and national level.

The sister projects ensure a holistic structure and approach to achieving the objectives of the Cancer mission and improving the quality of life of EU citizens.